

The Curvature Code - 8T

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main equation of the new 8T, and in particular the two pillar ideas, the first, the arbitrary variations term to vanish into matter, $\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0$. and the second, arbitrary variation term being at a positive summation state – representation of Bosonic emission $\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0$, we can solve the unknown chain of fourfold terms given by the main equation - $[\delta \ell \delta s \delta M] \delta g$. For Fermions and Bosons, the two pillar ideas are serving as auxiliary conditions that describe the nature of class of particles. We can reason fermions being point like, and Bosons independence propagation.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

In the 8T thesis we have derived the fermions are described as the arbitrary variation term that vanish into matter:

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

On the other hand, the bosons were regarded as net curvature of discrete prime amounts as described by the primorial, which add up to a positive summation, so they only way to eliminate them is to subtract from one another. That is in agreement with QFT idea of commutation relation. The term describing Bosons is (1.49):

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

Up until now, reader is probability familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. From here on out, we have a completely new paper. Suppose we allocate to the terms, additional terms according to each variable in the main equation. Now as a result we have those fourfold terms for fermions and Bosons accordingly:

$$[\delta \ell \delta s \delta M] \delta g = 0$$

$$[\delta \ell \delta s \delta M] \delta g > 0$$

We do not know what are the values of the three terms inside the bracket, however since we know to associate the conditions in equations (1.48) and (1.49) to be equal to zero and larger than zero, these are in essence constraint to the rest of the unknown chained terms. For fermions, we can deduce:

$$[\delta \ell \delta s \delta M] = 0$$

Because of the $\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0$ auxiliary condition, which impose a constraint on the chained terms. The fermions will receive the form of points, which are flat and are infinitesimal in length, on the matrix tensor of the manifold. Now analyze the Bosons, with the auxiliary condition $\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0$, the chained term is:

$$[\delta \ell \delta s \delta M] > 0$$

Bosons will receive the form of non-local propagation on the matrix tensor of the manifold. The opposite of infinitesimal scales, that is because they cannot vanish into matter, and isomorphic to prime numbers. Similar to how we presented the process of emission, described by the illustration in the next page.

Summing up, we do not know what are the chained three terms are, but we have proven the ideas two-pillar ideas of the 8T: (1.48) and (1.49) in which we can use, as auxiliary conditions. Those auxiliary conditions are used on the chained three terms, which we do not know, and thus they are the key to solve the entire chain. Those two conditions are the vital key to the curvature code – the language of nature.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)